

NDC ASPECTS

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What determines climate ambition? Analysing NDC enhancement with a mixed-method design (Deliverable 4.1)

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Preface

The NDC ASPECTS project will provide inputs to the Global Stocktake under the Paris Agreement (PA) and support the potential revision of existing Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) of the PA's parties, as well as development of new NDCs for the post 2030 period. The project will focus on four sectoral systems that are highly relevant in terms of the greenhouse gas emissions they produce yet have thus far made only limited progress in decarbonization. To advance these transformations will require to understand and leverage the Eigenlogic of those systems and take into account specific transformation challenges. These sectors are transport & mobility (land-based transport and international aviation & shipping), emission intensive industries, buildings, and agriculture, forestry & land-use, including their supply by and interaction with the energy conversion sector.

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1. Changes with respect to the DoW

We have made two changes with respect to the original Description of Work (DoW). First, we employ the Task 4 analytical framework, as stated in the DoW, but following a literature review on the drivers and barriers influencing climate policy ambition, we decided to focus on an up-to-date set of factors. Second, the DoW notes the use of target countries. While we analyse almost all target countries as part of the quantitative analysis, we have decided not to study the countries that did not submit an updated or revised NDC, as indicated in the DoW. Given the available resources, we did not conduct a qualitative analysis for all 20 countries. Instead, we decided to focus on four representative country cases and use the resources for an in-depth analysis of these four countries.

2. Dissemination and uptake

As detailed in the DoW and the project's Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, the deliverable will be made available on the project website and advertised via the project's social media channels. In addition, the results will be submitted to the journal *Climate Policy*.

The deliverable will be of use to different groups of stakeholders:

- Climate negotiators, who will be able to draw on the insights from this study in considering how the results of the global stocktake can be translated into more ambitious NDCs.
- National-level policymakers, particularly in the four case study countries, who can gain insights from this study on how national conditions can be made more amenable to enhancing subsequent NDCs.
- International and national civil society organisations, particularly in the four case study countries, who can identify ways in which they can help to influence more ambitious NDCs in future by understanding how NDCs were developed in the past.
- The academic community can build on this work to further improve the study of how are NDCs are developed and which factors influence NDC ambition.

3. Short summary of results

The study presents four key findings. First, based on prior academic and policy literature, we establish three categories of potential drivers and barriers of NDC enhancement: *political institutions*, *the economy*, and *structural factors*. Second, we identify the key role of democratic institutions through quantitative and qualitative methods. We find that more democratic countries were more likely to enhance their 2030 emission targets in the updated NDCs. The qualitative part of the deliverable supports this by finding that open and transparent stakeholder consultations were beneficial for the enhancement of greenhouse gas emission targets in updated NDCs. Saudi Arabia, however, is a key outlier as it enhanced its 2030 NDC mitigation target within completely closed decision-making institutions. Third, we establish that government and stakeholder concerns about the potential negative impacts of the green transition constitute a key barrier to continued NDC enhancement. The quantitative analysis shows that governments in countries with high economic fast-growing economies tended to keep their pledges the same or even reduced ambition. Qualitative interviews indicated that this may be due to worries about increasing GHG emissions and the effects of the low emission transition on future economic growth. The mixed-method findings suggest that the enhancement of climate pledges is sup-

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ported by open political processes that manage to take into account concerns about economic development. Finally, we do not find that structural factors, such as fossil fuel production and physical impacts of climate change constitute a significant barrier to NDC enhancement, although they may determine the initial level of climate ambition in the first NDC.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

The evidence of accomplishment of this deliverable is provided through the submission of this report. As detailed in the DoW, the main substantive content has been prepared in the form of an article manuscript.

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Executive Summary

The continual enhancement of climate commitments is a key aspect of the 2015 Paris Agreement. The Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) are an important part of the Paris Agreement's ratcheting mechanism aiming to ramp up climate change mitigation over time. However, little is still known if individual climate pledges have actually been enhanced over time and, if so, what the underlying drivers and barriers of more ambitious NDCs are. Addressing this gap, this study implements a mixed-methods design, employing both quantitative and qualitative methods. First, the paper identifies potential drivers of the strengthening of NDC targets, and tests whether these can account for differences in the enhancement of countries' mitigation targets under the Paris Agreement. Second, the paper investigates the drivers and barriers of NDC development qualitatively for key countries. We identify four case studies to accompany the quantitative part of the study: Brazil, Saudi Arabia, South Africa and the United States. The study identifies the key role of democratic institutions and stakeholder consultations for the enhancement of greenhouse gas emission targets in NDCs. We find that democratic countries are more likely to enhance their 2030 emission targets in the updated NDCs. The main driver of enhancement are more open and transparent institutions and stakeholder engagement. Saudi Arabia, however, is a key outlier as it enhanced its 2030 NDC mitigation target within completely closed decision-making institutions. Moreover, we find that worries about the potential negative impacts of the green transition constitute a key barrier. Governments in countries with high economic growth are less likely to improve their emission targets as they may worry that the transition to renewables may hamper further growth. We also find that the likelihood of NDC enhancement has grown over time as later NDC submissions more likely improve on previous targets. This gives some credence to Paris Agreement's "ratchet mechanism", whereby governments exceed their prior pledges over time. In summary, the mixed-method findings suggest that the enhancement of climate pledges is supported by open political processes that manage to take into account concerns about economic development.

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1 Introduction

The 2015 Paris Agreement requires countries to communicate their climate change mitigation goals by submitting plans of individual efforts in the form of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). Article 4(3) of the Paris Agreement states that each successive NDC submission is expected to be more ambitious than the previous one by representing “a progression beyond the Party’s then current nationally determined contribution and reflect[ing] its highest possible ambition” (UNFCCC 2015). The gradual ramping up of targets is expected to raise countries’ level of ambition to reach the Paris Agreement’s goal of limiting the rise of global average temperature to well below 2°C and pursuing efforts to stay below 1.5°C (UNFCCC 2015). The Paris Agreement sets up NDCs as an important benchmark of climate accountability as part of an international ratcheting mechanism (Falkner 2016, 1108). Nevertheless, countries are free to choose what pledges they make, and the Paris Agreement does not offer clear incentives compelling states to commit to sufficiently ambitious climate targets, nor are countries in danger of sanctions if their NDCs are not implemented or achieved.

Previous studies have begun to analyse the ambition level of NDCs (den Elzen et al. 2022; Khan 2019; Roelfsema et al. 2020; Vaidyula and Hood 2018), and also the factors that explain cross-country variation in NDC targets (Tørstad, Sælen, and Bøyum 2020; de Villafranca Casas et al. 2021). However, there is a dearth of studies that analyse both the overall drivers and barriers that influence the enhancement of consecutive NDCs. While prior studies have begun to assess the ambition of the first round of NDCs (Hsu et al. 2020; Stephenson et al. 2019), comparisons of updated and revised NDCs (submitted in 2020/2021) with initial submissions are still rare (with a few exceptions, e.g. Fransen, Ge, and Huang 2021; Mehrotra and Benjamin 2022). Our study aims to address this gap by exploring the role of political, economic and structural factors in determining the development of successive NDCs. Hence, we ask the following research question: Which drivers and barriers have led to the enhancement of updated NDCs?

The identification of how states have developed their revised or updated climate pledges enables a more comprehensive understanding of contemporary climate policy. In particular, this study is driven by the need for deeper insights into the change in the enhancement of NDCs to better understand the potential outcomes of the Paris Agreement and its likelihood to avert dangerous anthropogenic climate change. By 31 December 2021, 126 of the 193 Parties to the Paris Agreement submitted either a revised or updated NDC. The updated NDCs represented close to 99% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by COP26 in Glasgow (UNFCCC 2021). It is therefore timely to gain insights into how these revised and updated NDCs compare to the first round of NDCs, and what factors underpin NDC enhancement.

The analysis is carried out in two steps. First, the paper identifies several potential drivers and barriers of NDC enhancement, and tests whether these can account for the variation in mitigation targets under the Paris Agreement. Second, we provide a qualitative analysis of the drivers and barriers of NDC development for four critical cases (Flyvbjerg 2006). All of the country cases are members of the Group of 20 (G20) and make up a significant share of global GHG emissions, while representing significant variation in political and institutional configurations. The focus of the study rests on the determinants of NDC enhancement, rather than on their implementation.

The study contributes to the literature on climate politics in three ways. First, the study argues for using 2030 emission targets as a benchmark for assessing the robustness of the enhancement of updated/revised NDCs. We argue that this measure provides a robust and strict account of whether the

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updated or revised NDC is enhanced compared to the initial NDC submission. Second, the study presents a quantitative analysis of the drivers and barriers of enhanced NDC. Specifically, drawing on previous theoretical and empirical literature, we emphasise the role of *political institutions*, *the economy* and the *structural context*. Third, we employ the findings of the quantitative analysis and select four critical cases in relation to the quantitative results. The case studies support the large-*n* study by offering a more fine-grained analysis on the particular drivers and barriers that matter for NDC emission targets (Pickering, Bäckstrand, and Schlosberg 2020). The combination of the large-scale nature of the analysis combined with qualitative case studies aims at generating generalisable findings, which apply for a larger universe of cases.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the literature in relation to political institutions, the economy and structural context. Section 3 presents the research design, including both the quantitative analysis and the country case studies. Section 4 analyses the results of both steps of the study. Section 5 discusses both the quantitative and qualitative findings, and a concluding Section 6 summarises the results.

2 Literature review

The Paris Agreement follows a procedural approach in which countries are allowed to determine their own contribution to the global effort (Falkner 2016). This, however, leads to substantial variation in the commitments stated in NDCs (Pauw et al. 2018). As a consequence of each country's freedom to choose its own mitigation paths, we focus primarily on the domestic level, which has been considered the "cornerstone of the new global climate governance architecture" (Schulze 2021, 44). Nevertheless, prior studies have also shown that changes in climate commitments can be explained by international factors, such as regional and learning effects (Hildén 2011; Oberthür and Roche Kelly 2008; Zhou et al. 2019), transparency requirements (Pauw et al. 2018; Weikmans, van Asselt, and Roberts 2020), policy networks (Rennkamp and Boulle 2018) and general treaty design (Fankhauser, Gennaioli, and Collins 2014). Drawing on previous literature on domestic determinants, we identify three broad categories of drivers and barriers for the enhancement of climate commitments: *political institutions*, *the economy* and *structural context*. As we explain below, prior research suggests that these factors play a role at the domestic level.

2.1 Political institutions

First, the study will take into account the role of *political institutions*, since robust political institutions are a key precondition of the development of sufficiently ambitious NDCs (Röser et al. 2020). We will investigate, in particular, the effect of political institutions such as elections, democracy and partisanship. Schulze (2021) notes that there are both arguments for and against the effect of electoral cycles on change in climate ambition. Most notably, ambitious climate policy has been previously not considered a popular campaign promise (Fankhauser, Gennaioli, and Collins 2015). Nevertheless, environmental policies are not as unpopular as previously thought, as politicians tend to propose more environmental legislation prior to elections (McAlexander and Urpelainen 2020; List and Sturm 2006).

Prior research has also shown the positive influence of democracy on addressing environmental problems (Clulow 2019; Dasgupta and De Cian 2018; Pellegrini and Gerlagh 2006; Pickering et al. 2022). Democratic states are more likely to commit to international treaties (Carbonell and Allison 2015; Böhmelt and Butkutė 2018) and make more substantial promises to mitigate than non-democracies (Bättig and Bernauer 2009; Böhmelt, Böker, and Ward 2016; Burnell 2012). While studies have linked democracy to better policy outputs, such as more stringent policies, the link between democracy and climate policy outcomes, such as GHG emission reductions, is less clear (Selseng, Linnerud, and Holden 2022). Furthermore, the capability of democracies to propose more stringent international pledges may vary depending on their bureaucratic capacity (Meckling and Nahm 2022) and economic conditions (Povitkina 2018).

Previous studies theorise that democracies are more likely to produce more ambitious climate policy output for two key reasons (Clulow 2019, 246). First, democracies allow for the consultation of key stakeholders and maintain a more vibrant civil society. Stakeholder consultations are in essence considered more democratic (Bäckstrand 2006). The involvement of stakeholders increases the accountability of public policy to the general public (Lægreid and Povitkina 2018) and has shown to lead to more ambitious climate policy (Bernauer et al. 2016). In democratic countries, civil society organisations are allowed the political space to influence climate policy discussions, which is generally more limited in hybrid and autocratic regimes (Pacheco-Vega and Murdie 2021; Shahar 2015). Schultz and

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Crockett (1990) note that democracies allow environmental movements greater freedom in influencing policy. Consequently, Böhler et al. (2022) find that the successful mobilisation of interest groups in support of climate action leads to an increased adoption of climate laws.

Second, democracies are more transparent and sustain a free flow of information, which gives citizens better tools to hold their governments accountable for climate action (Fiorino 2018). Böhmelt et al. (2016) note that inclusiveness and open debate are the primary drivers of the ambitious climate policies of democracies. Previous research has shown that higher levels of societal awareness about climate change and public support for climate policy are associated with higher mitigation targets (Drummond et al. 2018; Rowan 2019). Transparent policies tend to result in better governance (Islam 2006).

Nevertheless, democracy can also restrict far-reaching international pledges. Researchers note the importance of free and fair elections (Barrett and Graddy 2000), and find that political competition and the fear of losing votes is vital for understanding climate policy in democracies and makes them more responsive to the needs of the public (Breetz, Mildenerger, and Stokes 2018; Kotov and Nikitina 1995; Schulze 2021). However, democratic governments may be also less inclined to propose overtly ambitious political goals by empowering organised business interests and industry groups that lobby for less climate action (Bernauer and Koubi 2009; Mildenerger 2020). Never and Betz (2014) find that a weakened environmental civil society *vis-à-vis* strong fossil fuel interests results in weak climate outcomes. Mildenerger (2020) shows in the case of the United States how powerful interest groups with deep pockets and a climate-sceptic agenda may have greater influence on an open policymaking process.

According to this logic, autocratic leaders would be less likely to be held accountable if proposed goals are ultimately not met. Furthermore, however, the responsiveness to the demands of the public can also lead to less ambitious climate policies, depending on the perceived cost of the policies to consumer and interest group pocketbooks (Finnegan 2021). Nevertheless, von Stein (2016) finds that democracies are more likely to implement their promises. In sum, democracies are found to enhance climate policies due to electoral competition, stronger environmental civil society organisations and more transparent modes of governance. Thus, we expect that more democratic countries are more likely to enhance their NDC targets.

The role of politics can also materialise in the form of partisanship. Much of the literature finds that government partisanship matters and that conservative/right-wing governments tend to oppose climate action (Dunlap and McCright 2015). However, studies also find that more left-wing governments are more likely to administer more ambitious national climate policies (Tobin 2017), but also adopt “hard” (Schulze 2021) and “more unifying” policies (Fankhauser, Gennaioli, and Collins 2014). Climate change is a highly partisan topic in many countries and climate policy output can change significantly as a result of key elections (Linde 2018). Thus, we account for government ideology during the period between the initial and revised/updated NDC as well, expecting that left-wing governments are more likely to enhance NDC targets.

2.2 The economy

The second category of drivers and barriers focuses on *the economy*, comprising key economic factors. First, we will investigate the role of economic growth. It is frequently assumed that governments in countries with low economic growth may prioritise economic objectives over potentially expensive climate action in the short term. Prolonged economic recessions, especially, are known to have led policymakers to lower national expectations in terms of climate policy (Gillard and Lock 2017). Skovgaard (2014) finds that the financial crisis of 2007 generally divided European Union (EU) countries

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into two camps: those that saw climate policy as beneficial and those that saw it as harmful for economic growth. Economic growth is one of the most important government policy objectives and may function as a signalling mechanism for both policymakers and stakeholders about how well the economy is doing. A flatlined or declining economy may steer policy priorities away from long-term plans on ambitious climate action by putting pressure on the government to improve economic performance (Cseh 2019), which leads to more carbon-intensive policy objectives in the short term. Hence, it can be expected that countries with negative economic growth may be less predisposed to submit an enhanced NDC, while countries with a growing economy may be more willing to invest in future-proofing their economy against future threats.

Second, the article also looks at the role of overall level of national income and economic development. Countries with fewer economic means would be expected to be more hesitant to submit highly ambitious NDCs due to the prospectively high-cost measures of decarbonisation. While prior research has also shown that countries' climate pledges tend to overcome the negotiation divide between developed Annex I and developing non-Annex I countries (Michaelowa and Michaelowa 2015), economic considerations play an important role in governments' strategic planning (Maor, Tosun, and Jordan 2017). Since a major public policy programme, such as climate change mitigation, requires access to significant financial resources (Salon, Murphy, and Sciara 2014), we expect that countries with more economic resources are more likely to submit more ambitious climate targets.

Finally, many developing countries have made their mitigation contributions conditional upon receiving international support (Pauw et al. 2020). Dash and Gim (2019) point out that developing countries have argued for enhancing climate targets on the expectation that this will leave them better placed for the provision of international climate finance. Many developing countries have submitted conditional NDC commitments, which are contingent on external financial assistance, mainly in the form of climate financing. Thus, we expect that the level of ambition in the revised or updated NDCs of developing countries is dependent on current trends in international climate financing.

2.3 Structural context

Third, we seek to explain the enhancement of NDC targets by means of the *structural context*. Governments' hands are often tied due to longstanding structural issues, which can make policymaking less agile or more difficult. Sprinz and Vaahtoranta (2008) argue that countries are highly dependent on two long-term drivers and barriers: vulnerability to climate change and the level of abatement costs. We will account for these factors through examining exposure to climate change and dependence on fossil fuels.

Existing studies have been inconclusive on whether more vulnerable countries in general are more likely to increase climate commitments (Peterson 2021; Tubi, Fischhendler, and Feitelson 2012). Nevertheless, the occurrence of extreme weather events has been shown to increase media coverage on climate change (Pianta and Sisco 2020), which may influence national policymaking (King, Schneer, and White 2017). We draw on the physical exposure to climate change through climate-related hazards rather than vulnerability since the latter concept incorporates economic and institutional components, which we aim to investigate independently. Hence, we expect that more affected countries would be more motivated to pick up the pace of their climate commitments and enhance their NDCs. As governments are confronted by the destruction from meteorological and hydrological hazards, such as storms, floods and droughts, they may shift to more ambitious climate action.

We take into account the "two-level game" introduced by Putnam (1988). According to this logic, international pledges are the result of a careful balancing act on two levels. Governments negotiate with

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stakeholders at the domestic level, while simultaneously negotiating with other governments at the international level. The fossil fuel industry, especially, commit substantial financial resources to obstruct climate policy by lobbying governments (Colgan, Green, and Hale 2021). Therefore, we also explore the potential pressure of the fossil fuel industry (i.e., coal, oil and natural gas production) at the national level, as it is most negatively affected by the transition to a low-emission development pathway. Hence, we account for the influence of the fossil fuel industry as a barrier to more ambitious climate policy. We expect that governments of countries with abundant fossil fuel resources find it more difficult to divert away from fossil fuel production due to the “carbon trap”, and are thus less likely to propose enhanced NDCs (Haley 2011; Manley, Cust, and Cecchinato 2017).

3 Research design

The study employs a mixed-method approach. We apply quantitative and qualitative methods in two phases, with each phase offering a different contribution. This approach allows us simultaneously to generalise based on the quantitative exercise and provide a more detailed analysis based on the case studies (Steinberg 2015). The mixed-method approach is beneficial for explaining the variation in the enhancement of NDC emission targets, since it allows us to analyse the drivers and barriers of NDC enhancement on the general international level, but also provide detail on specific NDC development processes part of the country cases.

In the first phase, we conduct logistic regression analysis to investigate the enhancement of NDC GHG emission targets for 2030. In the second phase of the analysis, we use qualitative analysis to examine four distinct country cases: Brazil, Saudi Arabia, South Africa and the United States. Hence, we are able to draw on the findings of the quantitative analysis for the purposes of analysing the four key cases. For the case studies, we use document analysis, triangulated by 14 expert interviews (Meuser and Nagel 2009). The multiple case study design has proven to be especially useful when comparing countries with vastly different political systems (Muriaas 2012). Multiple case studies, in addition to providing generalisable results (Flyvbjerg 2006), support our multi-method design mainly in two ways. First, the case studies support the validation of the measurement of the independent variables and the dependent variable. Second, the case studies help us observe potential omitted variables (Seawright 2016).

3.1 Method 1: Quantitative analysis

The quantitative part of the study employs cross-sectional data to analyse the enhancement of NDC GHG emission targets among 122 countries. The large-scale nature of the analysis contributes to the literature with generalisable findings across all updated or revised NDCs.

To operationalise our dependent variable, we need to provide an indication of the change in ambition between the initial NDC and the revised or updated NDC. Doing so poses significant challenges given the heterogeneity of NDCs, the targets contained therein, as well as the underlying methodologies and assumptions. Although a separate methodology can be developed to be applied to the various elements of NDCs (see e.g. de Villafranca Casas et al. 2021), an analysis of multiple elements would lead to difficult – and often subjective – choices about whether there has been a change in ambition. For instance, should adding new policies or covering new sectors and GHGs automatically constitute enhanced ambition? Some countries submitted initial NDCs that did not refer to GHG targets at all, but rather “strategies, plans and actions for low-emission development” (UNFCCC 2021, 25). If not, where should one draw the line? These are just some of the challenges that researchers would need to confront when developing their own methodology for assessing whether NDCs have been enhanced.

We build on data provided by the Climate Watch platform, managed by the World Resources Institute, to construct a dependent variable based on the proposed reduction of total GHG emissions by 2030 in the updated or revised NDC. In the creation of the dimensions of NDC target enhancement, we draw on Fransen et al. (2017) and Fransen, Ge and Huang (2021). Therefore, and keeping in mind the need for parsimony, for this study we code the NDCs as either 1 for “enhanced GHG emission target” or 0 for “no enhancement”. The dataset includes countries that submitted their first and revised or updated NDC during the period between March 2016 and December 2021. We do not account for countries that did not update their NDC during this timeframe as we cannot predict what their pledges would have been like otherwise.

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The sample comprises countries that submitted their updated and revised NDCs. The EU is analysed as a single unit since the commitments of its Member States are represented by a single EU-wide NDC. We average all of our variables across all EU Member States per year. In sum, 52% of the 122 updated and revised NDCs in our dataset enhanced their 2030 emission target. The use of this dependent variable is favourable for three reasons.

First, this measure accounts for dynamic target enhancement in relation to the original pledge, rather than static aggregate climate commitments. This allows us to investigate change in commitments and not the factors that cause changes in the overall level of climate action. Second, the indicator accounts for total emission reductions by 2030, which represents a more generalisable and stricter interpretation of NDC enhancement. Countries maintain considerable discretion over the revision of their NDCs, by strengthening and/or adding a GHG target; changing emission baselines and business-as-usual (BAU) scenarios; expanding the scope, target period, and coverage of the prior GHG target; and through the addition of new policies and measures (Fransen et al. 2017). Some of these additions may be highly stringent, while others are relatively undemanding. For instance, 25 countries in our dataset propose a net-zero target for the years 2030, 2050, 2060, or for a specific sector. However, it is difficult to compare these targets among themselves and with the rest of the sample. Moreover, distant net-zero targets may in some cases function as a stalling tactic. For instance, 13 of the updated NDCs that included a net-zero target did not enhance the more immediate 2030 emission target (e.g., Australia, Bhutan and Switzerland). Mitigation commitments, as translated into 2030 GHG emission reductions, is a reasonably rigorous measure, since it requires a quick response, and discounts attempts to change baselines (i.e., inflate the updated BAU scenario) in favour of the proposer. Sixty updated NDCs out of 122 made some type of changes to the BAU or base year calculations. Finally, the 2030 GHG emission target improvement allows for better comparison and covers more countries than similar databases, such as the Climate Target Update Tracker by Climate Action Tracker (CAT 2022; WRI 2022).

We use logistic regression to analyse variation in NDC enhancement across countries. We employ this particular method because of the dichotomous nature of the dependent variable: a country either enhances its NDC (1) or does not (0). Logistic regression aims to overcome two key conceptual problems associated with dichotomous dependent variables: nonlinearity and nonadditivity (Pampel 2020). First, compared to linear regression which expects a linear relationship between the independent variables (the drivers and barriers) and the dependent variable (NDC enhancement), logistic regression assumes that the effect of a unit change in the independent variable is smaller on the predicted probability (of NDC enhancement) near the lowest or highest values than near the middle of the range. Linear regression, in comparison, tends to overstate the relationship at the lowest and highest values, and understate the relationship in the middle of the range.

Second, logistic regression resolves the issue of nonadditivity, that the effect of an independent variable on the dependent variable stays the same regardless of the levels of the other independent variables (Pampel 2020, 8). In essence, very influential independent variables can push the probability of the dichotomous dependent variable very close to 0 or 1, which in effect does not allow other variables to have much influence. Additive regression models, such as linear regression, would incorrectly assume that the effect of a characteristic on NDC enhancement is identical for all levels of other variables. Moreover, logistic regression is more appropriate than linear regression for this study, since our dichotomous dependent variable violates the assumptions of normality, that the errors are normally distributed around the predicted Y, and homoscedasticity, that the dispersion of the error values for each X value is the same. We test models for the explanatory variables separately and we also test them in a step-wise manner in Appendix B, by adding each variable gradually into the model.

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First, for variables on *political institutions*, we account for democracy using the Polyarchy Index from the Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) database (Coppedge et al. 2022). The Polyarchy Index is an aggregate measure that evaluates electoral democracy on a scale between 0.018 and 0.922 for our sample of countries, with higher values representing a higher degree of suffrage, freedom of expression, freedom of association, the fairness of elections, but also indicating whether the executive is appointed through popular elections. Furthermore, we account for the consultation of civil society organisations based on an expert survey whether “major civil society organizations (CSOs) [are] routinely consulted by policymakers on policies” (Coppedge et al. 2022, 193). Using measures from V-Dem excludes smaller states in the full dataset (i.e., Andorra, Monaco, Nauru) and limits our sample to 111 countries. We measure government partisanship with an indicator (Left-wing Government) from the same database, which captures the extent the ruling government during the submission year of the updated NDC is socialist or communist (Tannenberget al. 2019). The indicator measures the “extent [to which] the current government promote[s] a specific ideology or societal model” based on country expert ratings, which is measured on a scale from 0 to 1 (Coppedge et al. 2022, 27).

Second, to capture the role of the *economy*, we use data from the World Bank on gross domestic product (GDP) per capita (measured in constant 2015 US dollars) and economic growth, both from the preceding year (t-1) before the submission of the updated NDC (World Bank 2022). We take the natural logarithm of GDP per capita due to the diminishing returns at higher levels of economic development. The measure for climate finance comes from the OECD Statistics database on climate-related external development finance flows (OECD 2022). It accounts for climate change mitigation flows received by developing countries, which are marked “significant” based on the Rio Markers as in previous studies (Peterson and Skovgaard 2019).

Third, for *structural factors*, we draw upon data on exposure to climate change from the University of Louvain EM-DAT database (CRED 2021). We subset the data for climate change-related events, such as storms, floods, landslides, wildfires and extreme temperature events. We employ data on the number of people affected *per capita* due to the aforementioned extreme weather events in the period between the initial and updated NDC. The data on fossil fuel rents comes from the World Bank, which is measured as the share of coal, oil and natural gas rents of GDP for the yearly average between the initial and the updated NDC. This measure accounts for the contribution of coal, oil and natural gas to national economic output (GDP).

Furthermore, we control for the submission year of the revised or updated NDC (2019, 2020 and 2021) since governments who submitted their NDCs more recently likely had access to more recent and improved scientific information on emission scenarios and potential development pathways. Alternatively, governments submitting later NDCs updates may have been influenced by either the strengthened or lowered ambition of prior NDC updates.

3.2 Method 2: Qualitative case studies

In the qualitative part of the study, we focus on four key country cases: Brazil, Saudi Arabia, South Africa and the United States. Our aim is to focus on a diverse set of critical cases (Yin 2013) as a way to triangulate and examine the findings from the quantitative analysis. Critical cases can be defined as “having strategic importance in relation to the general problem” (Flyvbjerg 2006, 229). The country cases are aimed to represent key political, economic and structural issues for the study of NDC enhancement. The chosen cases are especially opportune due to their characteristics, since they exhibit variation in the level of democracy, change in the quality of democratic institutions, dependence on

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fossil fuels and vulnerability to climate change. They cover different political regimes, presidential (Brazil and the US) and parliamentary (South Africa) democracies of varied democratic quality, and an absolute monarchy (Saudi Arabia), and represent ~18% of all GHG emissions in 2020. The country cases provide a good representation of the major G20 countries and represent a number of major negotiating blocks at the UNFCCC negotiations, such as BASIC (Brazil and South Africa), Arab States and the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (Saudi Arabia), OECD and the Annex I countries (the US). This also means that the enhancement of their climate commitments as climate leaders is likely to receive more international attention and stimulate or discourage the ambition of other like-minded countries (Parker and Karlsson 2018). We focus on the similarities and differences of the initial and the first updated NDC for the country cases in terms of the drivers and barriers. The aim here is to untangle the potential influence of political, economic and structural factors, or lack thereof, on the enhancement of the 2030 GHG emission target in each case.

To gather data on the cases, we draw on policy documents and reports on the development of NDCs, such as official NDC submissions, country policy documents and reports by local analysts and news media. We have supplemented this document analysis with 14 semi-structured interviews with policy experts, scientists, civil society and private sector representatives, who were either involved in or have close knowledge of the development processes of the NDCs in the four countries. The names of the interviewees are kept anonymous due to the sensitivity of data and the role of some of the individuals in the development of the NDCs. The most important assertions by the interviewees were triangulated with other sources to guarantee their accuracy. See the Appendix E for the list of interviewees.

The case studies allow us to provide an in-depth exploration of the underlying mechanisms in the relationship between enhanced NDC emission targets and political, economic and structural factors. This allows us to situate the findings of the regression analyses in the political, economic and structural context of multiple countries and provides additional explanatory leverage, whilst at the same time sketching the broader narrative of how several revised or updated NDCs have come about. The qualitative method offers more fine-grained evidence on key variables and allows us to fill potential gaps and nuances that may have gone unnoticed by the quantitative part of the study. It also allows us to overcome the inevitable reliance on cross-country measures that enable parsimony and strengthen external validity but may not capture all dimensions of important factors.

4 Quantitative analysis

The results of individual models for all political, economic and economic factors can be seen in Figure 1. Each logistical regression model is run separately to test the impact of each factor on the dependent variable of the enhancement of 2030 emission targets in the updated NDCs.

First, we investigate the role of *political institutions*. Figure 1 shows the estimate for each variable separately on the enhancement of the 2030 targets. Table 1 presents the results of electoral democracy (Polyarchy) as part of logistic regression models. The results show that electoral democracy has a statistically positive relationship with the enhanced NDC targets at the 0.05 level. Countries with more democratic political institutions are more likely to enhance their NDCs. In models (2) and (3) of Table 1, we can also see that this relationship is independent from the level of economic development (GDP per capita) and the time period (NDC update year) that the updated or revised NDC was submitted in.

Logistic regression coefficients are presented in terms of logged odds (the logarithm of ratio of probabilities), which are relatively unintuitive for understanding social science phenomena (Best and Wolf 2013, 155–57). However, we can interpret the democracy coefficient as probabilities at different levels of polyarchy by transforming log odds to probabilities based on the average level of GDP per capita in our dataset. In model (3) the least democratic countries (i.e., Qatar and Saudi Arabia, with an electoral democracy score ~ 0.08) are $\sim 41\%$ likely to enhance the emission targets of updated or revised NDCs. Low-ranked countries by the electoral democracy index (~ 0.5), such as Albania and Kenya, have a $\sim 50\%$ probability to enhance the targets of their NDC pledges. Less democratic countries (electoral democracy score ~ 0.75), such as South Africa are 73% likely to improve on their initial NDC emission target, while highly democratic countries (i.e., electoral democracy score ~ 0.9 on the level of New Zealand and the United States) are 79% likely to enhance their pledge. The Akaike information criterion (AIC), an estimator of the relative information value of the model, increases slightly in Table 1 from Model 1 to Model 2, but decreases in Model 3. Including GDP per capita slightly improves the explanatory power of the model, but the year of the NDC update decreases it. This suggests that the best-fit model was Model 2, which excludes the submission year.

It is difficult to disentangle the role of elections from other democratic institutions, since almost all electoral democracies held presidential (presidential democracies) or parliamentary elections (parliamentary democracies) in the inter-NDC period between the initial and the updated or revised NDC. The only exceptions are Cabo Verde, Jamaica and Suriname, where fresh elections closely followed the submission of the update. We also find that the estimate for the left-wing ideology of the ruling government is negative but not statistically significant, which suggests the null hypothesis – that more left-wing governments are not more likely to enhance NDCs, at least when measured on the international level.

Second, for economic factors, Table 2 shows that countries with negative economic growth in the year preceding the submission of the updated NDC are less likely to propose enhanced 2030 emission targets (at the 0.05 level of statistical significance). This finding remains robust even when GDP per capita (log), democracy and government ideology are accounted for in the same model. However, Table 2 demonstrates that the estimate is statistically not significant when a control for the year of the updated NDC is included. This is caused likely due to unobserved economic trends (i.e., COVID-19 and changes in oil prices) and a lack of variation across time. Hence, economic growth is likely to play an unfavourable role for the enhancement of GHG targets, but this is sensitive to overall economic trends. Governments of fast-developing economies tend to have swiftly growing GHG emissions and may be

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prone to lowering their expectations of emission reductions in the future due to the difficulties associated with decoupling. A similar dynamic has been noted on the local level in China (Wang et al. 2021). Growing economies may be more sensitive to the conflict between classical modes of economic growth and enhanced climate action. Similarly, Ahmadanov and van der Borg (2019) find that higher economic growth is associated with lower renewable energy production as rapidly growing economies may require a larger supply of energy than may be currently delivered by renewable energy projects. Prior literature has also previously found the perceived economic costs to be the main obstacles to the adoption of renewables (Jewell and Cherp 2020). The countries with the highest economic growth from the year preceding to the submission of the updated NDC were Rwanda (6.6% in 2019), Monaco (6.1%), and Vietnam (6%). Countries with declining economies in 2020 (-5.2% fall, i.e., North Macedonia) are 61% likely to improve their NDC GHG emission target, while rapidly growing economies (5.6% growth, i.e., Mongolia) are in comparison 55% likely to enhance their NDC pledge. As in Table 1, the AIC estimates in Table 2 suggests that the best-fit model was Model 2, which excludes the submission year.

Figure 1. Results of the quantitative analysis.

The dependent variable is the enhancement of the 2030 GHG emission target in the updated NDC (dichotomous). Fossil fuel rents (oil+coal+gas), receipt of climate finance, and the number of people affected by climate hazards are taken as an average value between the submission of the NDCs. Economic growth is lagged by one year from the updated NDC (NDC2). All other variables are measured from the year of the submission of the updated NDC (NDC2). Point estimates are coefficients from separate bivariate logistic regression models. Horizontal lines are uncorrected 95% confidence intervals.

The estimates for the other economic and structural factors are not statistically distinguishable from zero. Hence, we find support for the null hypothesis that government partisanship, fossil fuel rents, the receipt of climate finance (among receivers), the number of people affected by climate hazards,

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and national income (GDP per capita) do not affect the enhancement of NDCs. Although prior research has shown the adverse effect of fossil fuel rents on NDC targets (Tørstad, Sælen, and Bøyum 2020), we find a negative but not statistically significant role for NDC enhancement. Hence, fossil fuel rents do not seem to restrict NDC enhancement – at least in the first round of updates and revisions. This is maybe the case because countries with substantial fossil fuel rents exhibited overall lower commitment to climate action – *ceteris paribus* – in their initial NDCs. GDP per capita exerts a positive but statistically insignificant effect on NDC enhancement, both taken on its own and along with other variables. This, however, does not mean that overall ambition levels may differ between developed and developing countries. The rest of the statistically insignificant factors may affect overall ambition but do not influence NDC enhancement in our sample.

However, we find that the estimate for the submission year of the updated NDC is positive and statistically significant in all models. This means that the later the NDC update was submitted, the more likely it was that the government improved its 2030 target for total GHG emission. This result is likely due to better access to scientific knowledge, such as improved global and national 2030 emission trajectories. Later submitters can be assumed to have better knowledge about the impacts of climate change, emission baselines and scenarios. The positive role of continuously improving scientific knowledge has also been shown in the case of the Montreal Protocol (Albrecht and Parker 2019). In addition, this finding supports the performance of Paris Agreement’s “ratchet mechanism”, since later NDC updates are more likely to enhance their 2030 targets than earlier submissions. This lends credibility to the general expectation that governments are inspired by the positive examples of prior NDCs and tend to continually improve their targets.

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Table 1. Electoral democracy and NDC 2030 Emission Target Enhancement.

Electoral democracy: regression models			
	Dependent variable:		
	2030 emission target enhancement		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Electoral democracy (Polyarchy)	0.468** (0.188)	0.414** (0.203)	0.432** (0.198)
GDP per capita (log)		0.025 (0.036)	0.039 (0.035)
NDC update submission year			0.249*** (0.095)
Constant	0.303*** (0.103)	0.117 (0.279)	-503.987*** (191.317)
Observations	111	111	111
Akaike Inf. Crit.	160.539	162.016	157.037
<i>Note: Standard errors in parentheses</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table 2. Economic Growth and NDC 2030 Emission Target Enhancement.

Economic growth: regression models			
	Dependent variable:		
	2030 emission target enhancement		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
GDP growth (% change, t-1)	-0.017** (0.007)	-0.015** (0.007)	-0.006 (0.009)
GDP per capita (log)		0.037 (0.033)	0.061* (0.036)
NDC update submission year			0.216* (0.121)
Constant	0.496*** (0.048)	0.193 (0.278)	-435.623* (244.568)
Observations	117	117	117
Akaike Inf. Crit.	170.055	170.807	169.565
<i>Note: Standard errors in parentheses</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

The robustness tests are included in Appendices B and C. Studies have also shown the adverse effect of corruption on climate policy (Cole 2007; Povitkina 2018), which is accounted for with the Worldwide Governance Indicators corruption index as part of robustness testing in Appendix C. We find that the estimate for the quality of government was not significant at the 0.05 level and led to a drastically reduced sample size. Hence, it was not included as a control variable. Furthermore, the AIC, which shows how well the model fits the data, is highest for the first model with only electoral democracy, while the stepwise addition of each new variable tends to reduce model fit. The differences in AIC between the models are small, however.

The role of democracy and economic growth requires further exploration. In particular, we need to look at which specific features of democratic institutions (i.e., free and fair elections, open consultations and civil society, and free flow of information) were instrumental for the submission of more ambitious NDCs. Next, we turn to the case studies of the development of updated or revised NDCs.

5 Case studies

The country case studies compare the development of the first and the updated NDC with regard to changes in political institutions, the economy and structural context, as relevant for the case.

Table 3. Summary of headline targets for Brazil, Saudi Arabia, South Africa and the United States.

Country	Brazil	Saudi Arabia	South Africa	USA
First NDC 2030 target	Reduce GHG emissions by 37% in 2025, and by 43% (indicative) in 2030 below 2005 levels	NA	“South Africa's emissions by 2025 and 2030 will be in a range between 398 and 614 MtCO ₂ eq”	26% to 28% reduction of GHG emission by 2025 compared to 2005 and to make best efforts to reduce its emissions by 28%
Updated NDC target	Brazil commits to reduce emissions from 2005 levels by 37% in 2025, and by 50% in 2030.	“Thus, the renewable energy ambition aims to reach around 50% of the energy mix by 2030” “By 2030, the Kingdom aims that up to 50% of its electricity generation is expected to be met by natural gas significantly lowering the carbon intensity of domestic energy generation”	“South Africa commits to reducing its GHG emissions to 398-510 MtCO ₂ e by 2025, and to 350-420 MtCO ₂ e by 2030”	"Economy-wide target of reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by 50-52 percent below 2005 levels in 2030"
Target type in NDC update	GHG mitigation target relative to base year	Non-applicable (non-) GHG target	GHG mitigation target based on fixed emission levels	GHG mitigation target relative to base year
NDC enhancement	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

5.1 Brazil

The first Brazilian NDC was submitted in September 2016 during the Dilma Rousseff administration, while the first updated NDC was submitted in December 2020 during the Jair Bolsonaro administration. The updated NDC proposes an unconditional decrease of emissions by 50% by 2030 (43% in the first NDC). According to international coverage, Climate Watch and interviewed experts, the updated NDC, despite presenting a decrease of emissions on paper, is less ambitious than the initial NDC from 2016. The emissions accounting for the 2005 GHG emission levels in the updated NDC was raised *ex post* to allow for higher emissions in order to meet targets (Unterstell and Martins 2022). The updated NDC also “considers achieving carbon neutrality in 2060”, and given the need may even consider “a more ambitious long-term objective in the future, having as a time horizon, for instance, the year 2050”. The updated target provides very little information about the measures needed to attain the results.

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The development of both the first and the updated NDC was entrusted to the Ministry of Environment. The development process of both the initial and the updated NDC also included the Ministry of Mines and Energy, Foreign Affairs, and the Office of the Chief of Staff of the Presidency (interviewees #11 and #14). Climate negotiations prior to the initial NDC were also led by the Ministry of Science and Technology, which produced a report on Brazilian mitigation scenarios regarding potential ambition and mitigation technologies in the transport, industry, buildings, power, and waste and residues sectors. However, due to inter-ministerial rivalry, the Ministry of Environment did not have access to the main report and relied on additional studies on the energy sector by *Empresa de Pesquisa Energética*, a public company linked to the Ministry of Mines and Energy, and on deforestation by the *Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais*, an aeronautical research organisation (interview #2). The production of key scientific insights, such as emission inventories and scenarios informed inter-ministerial and stakeholder discussions about NDCs (interviewees #1 and #2). Stakeholder dialogue before the initial NDC took place through the Brazilian Forum on Climate Change, a government-backed climate forum, to formulate a national plan for climate commitments (Reuters 2019). In the next paragraphs, we will cover the key domestic drivers and barriers of NDC enhancement in Brazil.

The role of political institutions and the ideology of the President are crucial for Brazil's climate action. Climate change has been a relatively important topic for candidates in previous years (Franchini, Mauad, and Viola 2020). Bolsonaro promised to withdraw Brazil from the 2015 Paris Agreement and open up the Amazon to increased deforestation during his election campaign (Escobar 2018). While Brazil did not pull out from the Paris Agreement and submitted an updated NDC, the hostility of his administration to further climate action has been clear. Bolsonaro's government abolished the Secretariat for Climate Change and Forests, the agency responsible for action on climate change, and has hindered the participation of civil society in policymaking. The eventual submission of the updated Brazilian NDC in 2020 came about due to continued support from the Ministries of Environment and Agriculture, and pressure from industrial and energy groups that were concerned about international backlash (interviewee #13). The development process of the updated NDC, however, was conducted in an opaque manner, with a restricted and underfunded Brazilian Forum on Climate Change for stakeholder involvement. An overall decline in policy transparency and NDC development process is consistent with democratic backsliding in Brazil during Bolsonaro's government (Alizada et al. 2022).

The key economic barriers to a more ambitious NDC according to interviewees were the perceived threat to economic development and jobs. The Brazilian Forum on Climate Change consulted extensively with the scientific community, business groups (especially in the agrobusiness and forestry sectors), non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and labour unions for the initial NDC (interviewee #1). However, the Forum did not involve sub-national actors to a significant extent (interviewee #14). Before the forum, the Ministry of Environment also engaged in bilateral discussions with agrobusiness and forestry companies. High-emitting industries were especially worried about jobs and losing out to competitors in China, while environmental NGOs were more supportive of the most ambitious mitigation scenarios. Nevertheless, the discussion on proposed scenarios remained amicable and different groups agreed about the potential of green jobs in the future (interviewee #2). However, the 2021 updated NDC was conducted behind closed doors without the explicit involvement of the scientific community (interviewees #1 and #13). The WWF (2020) reports that the members of the Brazilian Forum on Climate Change were not consulted about the updated NDC proposal. Continued work on updating the NDC was supported by business actors (interviewee #14).

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Structural factors did not play a major role in Brazil's NDC update. With regard to fossil fuel dependence, Brazil is in a relatively favourable position since it generates 66% of its electricity from hydro-power due to an abundance of rivers and lakes (Barros, Piekarski, and De Francisco 2018). Instead, the most contentious mitigation issue during the development process of the NDCs pertained to agriculture and deforestation (interviewees #2 and #11), given that land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF) and agriculture are two of the biggest sources of CO₂ emissions in Brazil (66% in 2020) (Garofalo et al. 2022). Only in 2021, a total of 1.5 million hectares were lost in Brazil, which makes up more than 40% of the deforestation of global tropical primary forest (Weisse and Goldman 2022). Bolsonaro's administration has been mired in scandals due to the withholding of deforestation data, as 13,235 square kilometres of rainforest were lost between August 2020 and August 2021 alone (Débora Álvares 2021). The *bancada ruralista* – a cross-party political caucus of federal deputies and senators who promote the interests of agribusinesses in congress – has gained influence and power under Bolsonaro's administration (interviewee #8).

Brazil is highly vulnerable to the effects of climate change. The number of wildfires has risen from 2014 and reached 222,798 wildfire occurrences, which is the result of human activity, drier weather and the lack of implementation of environmental safeguards (Pivello et al. 2021). Temperature changes and sea-level rise may alter the Amazon's ecosystem, impact the range of species and increase the frequency and intensity of droughts (Marengo et al. 2018). Nevertheless, none of our Brazilian interviewees found that extreme weather events and the threat of climate change had a role in the consultations or played only a significant role in the development of NDCs.

5.2 Saudi Arabia

The first NDC of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) was submitted in November 2016 and the updated submission was introduced in October 2021. The updated NDC from 2021 enhances the initial emission target by aiming to reduce, avoid, and remove “GHG emissions by 278 million tons of CO₂eq annually by 2030”, although without a baseline scenario (KSA 2021, 2). The omission of a baseline/BAU was likely intentional (interviewee #3). KSA also sets out a non-GHG target based on increasing the share of renewable energy “to reach around 50% of the energy mix by 2030”; and “[b]y 2030, the Kingdom aims that up to 50% of its electricity generation is expected to be met by natural gas significantly lowering the carbon intensity of domestic energy generation” (KSA 2021, 4, 5). While the updated NDC enhances the emission target for 2030, it makes it clear that it does not intend to reduce its oil exports, and that implementation is contingent on economic growth and diversification (KSA 2021, 2). We cover the key domestic drivers and barriers of NDC enhancement in Saudi Arabia in the following paragraphs.

The political system of the KSA is an absolute monarchy, where the king is chosen among the male descendants of Abdulaziz “Ibn Saud”, the founder of Saudi Arabia (Freedom House 2021). Salman bin Abdulaziz Al Saud is the current king of Saudi Arabia, who in 2017 appointed his son Mohammed bin Salman as crown prince and *de facto* ruler. The political regime can be characterised as autocratic, as there are few civil liberties, no political parties and no free press.

The development process of both the initial (2016) and the updated NDC (2021) was overseen by the Ministry of Energy, the state-owned fossil fuel producer Saudi Aramco, and the Presidency of Meteorology and Environmental (PME). Due to personal relations, key individuals in the PME played a more influential role in the development of the NDC than the Ministry of Energy (interviewee #3). Saudi Aramco, while *de facto* dependent on the Ministry of Energy, retained a significant level of autonomy in the inter-agency deliberation process (interviewee #4). The emission baselines and scenarios of both

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NDCs were informed by background research conducted by scientific consultants. However, the consultants were not given an opportunity to comment on the final draft. As such, the KSA NDCs are largely the result of closed-door deliberations between ministry officials and key decision-makers. The World Bank (2016) confirms that no stakeholder engagement, including with the private sector, took place to develop the 2016 NDC, which was also the case for the updated NDC (interviewee #4). While the development process precluded civil society actors, government officials confidentially consulted influential individuals from Saudi “industrial cities”, researchers from the state-funded King Abdullah Petroleum Studies and Research Center (KAPSARC) and the King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST) (interviewee #4).

Political institutions act as both drivers and barriers to NDC enhancement in the case of Saudi Arabia. As a consequence of being one of the world’s largest fossil fuel producers, KSA’s official stance at international climate negotiations has been historically obstructionist (Depledge 2008). KSA’s climate commitments are mostly driven by consideration of its international reputation. Nevertheless, Saudi leadership has shown greater willingness to cooperate on the international level since the appointment of Mohammed bin Salman as the crown prince (interviewees #3 and #4), who in 2016 called for ending the Kingdom’s “addiction to oil” (Reuters 2016). In 2021, KSA also declared that it will reach net-zero emissions by 2060 at the launch of the Middle East Green Initiative Summit, a regional alliance on sustainability and climate action (Saudi Green Initiative 2021). Since Saudi Arabia does not hold elections, allow for political competition, or provide for open stakeholder consultations, NDC enhancement is highly dependent on domestic economic considerations, which are discussed next.

Economic factors and the structural issue of fossil fuel rents are deeply related in the case of Saudi Arabia. Economic arguments play an important role for the NDCs as worries about economic growth combined with enormous fossil fuel rents, are an important barrier for further climate action. The country’s economy is highly dependent on the extraction and sale of fossil fuels. KSA holds 17% of the world’s oil reserves, and an estimated 40% of GDP derives from oil production and exports (Krane 2019). In 2019, Saudi Arabia ranked tenth in terms of total annual GHG emissions with 723.15 MtCO_{2e} (Climate Watch 2022). Furthermore, Saudi Aramco is responsible for a large part of current and historical emissions, contributing to 4.33% of global GHG gas emissions from 1965 to 2018 (Heede 2020). In the development process of the NDCs, KSA authorities emphasised the need to frame the NDCs in terms of economic diversification, non-GHG targets and climate co-benefits. One of the objectives of the NDCs is to steer the overall focus away from the mitigation of KSA’s total GHG emissions and redirect it, instead, towards pledges on improving energy efficiency and diversifying the economy away from fossil fuels (interviewee #3). As such, the government promotes the “circular carbon economy framework”, which puts particular attention on carbon capture and storage, natural sinks and energy efficiency, instead of reducing the supply of hydrocarbons (Shehri et al. 2022; interviewee #3).

In terms of vulnerability to climate change, Saudi Arabia is one of the most water-stressed countries in the world, which is likely to be exacerbated due to raising temperatures (Hofste, Reig, and Schleifer 2019). Nevertheless, interviewee #3 and #4 both did not find that the threat of climate impacts is an issue that could sway KSA’s current climate policy. Seawater desalination contributes 61% of the domestic water demand (Alnajdi, Wu, and Kaiser Calautit 2020) and the future of water access is not seen as a major political topic on the national level (interviewee #4). Instead, water access is perceived as a policy issue solvable through increased desalination.

5.3 South Africa

The first South African NDC was submitted in November 2016 during the Presidency of Jacob Zuma, and the updated submission was posted in September 2021 during the Presidency of Cyril Ramaphosa. The initial NDC expressed already existing climate policy and did not involve novel analytical work (interviewees #5 and #6). The updated South African NDC from 2021, however, involved new net-zero scenarios based on a “peak, plateau and decline” approach to future GHG emissions (interviewee #6). The upper end of the target range for the year 2030 was reduced by 32%, and the lower range by 12% compared to the initial NDC (398–614 MtCO₂eq by 2030). Central policies include the Integrated Resource Plan (approved 2019) and the Renewable Energy Independent Power Producers Procurement Programme.

The NDC development process involved Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE, previously DEA), which led the development process for both the initial and updated NDC along with the Department of Mineral Resources and Energy (DMRE), and the Department of International Relations and Cooperation (DIRCO). The process involved technical analysis, consultation within government, consultation with broader stakeholders, provincial public stakeholder workshops, finalisation in government and cabinet (South Africa 2021, 19–20; DFFE 2021a). We cover the key domestic drivers and barriers of NDC enhancement in South Africa in the following paragraphs.

In terms of political factors, climate change has not been a major electoral issue in South Africa. Rather, climate policy is the result of deliberations within African National Congress (ANC) party leadership, bureaucracy and key stakeholders (interviewees #5, #6 and #7). Overall, the inauguration of President Ramaphosa in 2018 saw an increase in more open political processes. The development of the updated NDC was more open to stakeholders than the development of the initial NDC. Ramaphosa established the Presidential Climate Commission (PCC) in February 2021, which brought together 22 commissioners from government, business organisations, civil society, organised labour and the scientific community to review the draft of the NDC update (DFFE 2021b; South Africa 2021). The PCC consultations played a key role in enhancing the updated NDC targets, which shifted the balance in favour of more climate ambition (Trollip 2021), compared to more sceptical government institutions, such as DIRCO and the Department of Trade and Industry (interviewees #5, #6 and #7). Stakeholders part of the PCC agreed about reducing South Africa’s overreliance on fossil fuels, but disagreed about the specific targets and measures to attain them. Stakeholder engagement was limited for the initial NDC and managed by the International Governance office of the DFFE, which heads South Africa at the UNFCCC negotiations (interviewee #5). Nevertheless, it is important to note that the initial NDC was built on earlier analytical work and engagement conducted for the 2015 intended NDC in line with its 2009 Copenhagen pledge.

Economic factors played a significant role during stakeholder consultations amid concerns about unemployment and economic decline (Trollip 2021, 6), as South Africa’s economy contracted by 6.4% in 2020 (World Bank 2022). Labour organisations opposed the closing of coal-fired power plants and collaborated with big emitters (interviewee #6). The Congress of South African Trade Unions (COSATU) has been reluctantly supportive of this energy transition out of concern over substantial job losses adding to the already high unemployment (Lenferna 2020, COSATU 2019, Pamla 2021, Field 2021, 259). Particularly, mining and metalworkers’ unions showed an unwillingness to team up with environmental organisations (Upadhyaya et al. 2021, 137). COSATU was one of the key proponents of a just transition to a low-carbon economy that protects workers from loss of livelihoods, which fully integrated into the NDC update (interviewee #12). Several interviewees noted that the inclusion of a just

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transition in the NDC update text helped get labour organisations on board (interviewees #6 and #12). Moreover, all interviewees noted that by the time of the NDC update the stance of the big emitters had shifted from obstruction to restrained collaboration. Business actors had become more proactive and admitted the need for changes. This development was supported by the decreasing cost of renewable energy (Tyler and Hochstetler 2021, 195) and fundamental changes in international trade (interviewees #5 and #7). Despite the consultative process, civil society has been critical of the updated NDC (Nkrumah 2021). For instance, the youth was side-lined in the decision-making process (Mazomba, Klaasen, and Farrell 2021).

The enhanced targets of the NDC were regarded as supportive for attracting more international climate finance (Mazomba, Klaasen and Farrell 2021, LAC 2021a, interviewee #12). Moreover, Eskom viewed the updated NDC and COP26 as an opportunity to secure new international financial support for its just energy transition. South Africa, along with the UK, the US, France, Germany and the EU announced a Just Energy Transition Partnership, which calls for international funding to support South Africa's decarbonization and achieve a just transition for economic sectors negatively affected by climate policies, such as mining, energy, manufacturing and transport (COP26 2021). The Partnership is part of a package of policy reforms that aim to support a just transition to a low-carbon economy. While the expectation of international climate finance, in general, may not have given rise to a push for including conditionality to the updated NDC (interviewee #5), it was felt that further international financing was needed to achieve the climate targets, according to a representative of business organisations (interviewee #7).

In terms of structural context, one of the principal barriers to enhancing climate action is South Africa's high dependence on coal-fired power. The state-owned and vertically integrated utility company Eskom controls the energy sector and is a central political actor along with Sasol and the energy-intensive industry (Orthofer, Huppmann, and Krey 2019). However, mismanagement, corruption and state capture have resulted in major blackouts since 2008. Eskom's debt crisis has created an urgent need for modernisation and diversification of the energy sector (Field 2021, 253; Orthofer, Huppmann, and Krey 2019, 1–2). Prices for renewable energy have generally fallen and together with high domestic solar energy rendered it a competitive alternative to coal (Field 2021, 256, 259). Nevertheless, climate change is not a major electoral issue due to the dominance of the ANC in post-apartheid South Africa. Instead, climate policy is largely influenced by deliberations within ANC party leadership, bureaucracy and Eskom (Tyler and Hochstetler 2021, 188). Together with other important domestic fossil fuel companies, Eskom has now become more committed to a coal phase-out and a transformation to renewable energy (DFFE 2021b).

5.4 United States

After re-joining the Paris Agreement in January 2021, the US submitted its first (new) NDC in April 2021. The NDC pledges to reduce GHG emissions by 50-52% below 2005 levels by 2030. Thereby, the new NDC strengthened its mitigation target compared to the first NDC from September 2016, which was posted by the Obama Administration. The new NDC was prepared in record time by the incoming Biden Administration, with six months from election day and three months from inauguration day (Chemnick 2021). Actual drafting of the NDC began only in March 2021 and was done in a hurry to finalise it for President Biden's Leaders' Summit on Climate (White House 2021).

The development of the NDC was led by the White House. Incoming President Joe Biden issued Executive Order 14008 in January 2021, which sets out a general framework for the planning process and institutions. This process consisted of a bottom-up analysis of existing and potential policies and

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measures at the federal level, accounting for capital stock turnover, technology trends, infrastructure needs, and continued subnational policies and measures. The core institutions involved were a newly created National Climate Task Force, the position of the National Climate Adviser and the White House Office for Domestic Climate Policy. The latter was in charge of the sector-by-sector assessments of mitigation potential and is headed by the National Climate Advisor (Gina McCarthy) and its Deputy (Ali Zaidi), but otherwise does not have predetermined staff. The National Climate Advisor also serves as the chair of the National Climate Task Force, which brings together representatives from 21 federal agencies (including the Environmental Protection Agency) and departments to facilitate the whole-of-government approach employed by president Biden (Executive Office of the President 2021; USA 2021). In November 2020, John Kerry was also announced as Special Presidential Envoy for Climate with a focus on international climate policy.

Regarding political factors, climate change as a policy issue continues to be strongly entrenched in partisan hostilities since the mid-2000s. However, the topic did not play a major role in the 2016 election campaign (MacNeil and Paterson 2020, 1, 4). In the 2020 elections, by contrast, climate change was one of the four initial policy priorities, and Biden quickly fulfilled some of his campaign pledges by re-entering the Paris Agreement and announcing his key climate policies (Choi 2021). Bodansky (2021) argues that more ambitious emission targets of the updated NDC were partly driven by the desire to regain international climate leadership. Without the submission of sufficiently stringent targets re-commitment would not have been considered credible by international actors (interviewee #9).

NDC development was based mainly on intergovernmental consultations and a whole-of-government approach (USA 2021, 10). Stakeholder consultations took place in a limited capacity due to the short deadline (interviewee #9). In March 2021, at the outset of the NDC development, the Biden administration met among others with representatives of utilities, car manufacturers, oil and aviation industry to identify possibilities for a joint effort based on their plans and visions for the future. The White House concentrated on consulting with key constituents in industry, labour organisations, green groups (i.e., Environmental Defense Fund, Natural Resources Defense Council, and the Union of Concerned Scientists), and subnational groups (cities and state actors). Reportedly, the election campaign team reached out to green groups, young activists and labour unions in spring 2020 (Brady and Grandoni 2020). Particularly, in January 2021 high-ranking officials from the US Climate Alliance met with the National Climate Advisor to strengthen the cooperation between federal and state level (USCA 2021). Nevertheless, climate and environmental justice activists are said to have a greater influence on the Biden administration than other movements (Aton 2021a, Mulkern 2021).

Economic interests were a key issue as part of the development of the NDC. Labour organisations and industry were especially worried about potential job losses (interviewee #9). Multiple analyses from environmental think tanks called for at least 50% below 2005 as a mitigation target that would be both feasible and internationally credible (Tollefson 2021). A scientific study of the potential impact of existing measures coupled with comprehensive federal and sub-federal level action also identified a margin of 46–52% as feasible (Hultman et al. 2020, 6). The We Mean Business Coalition (2021), a group of hundreds of pro-climate companies, communicated their support for at least 50% reductions relative to 2005 by 2030 to the president in mid-April. While the open letter likely did not influence the emission target directly, it along with other analyses and proposals, such as by the Environmental Defense Fund (EDF 2021), provided insight of the support for feasible emission reduction objectives (interviewee #10). The calls for a 50% reduction by businesses, civil society and academia signalled the government about the latitude for a potential 2030 target, which would be accepted as ambitious enough by different interest groups (interviewee #9).

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In terms of the structural context, fossil fuel interests play an important role in the US (Hermwille and Sanderink 2019). Slightly more than 80% of US primary energy comes from fossil fuels, mostly gas and oil (85% in 2020), with a slowly decreasing trend. The share of electricity production from fossil fuels has been declining since 2010 from 70% to 60% in 2021. Nevertheless, according to a White House official, the NDC resulted partly from changing market dynamics, particularly the lower cost of solar energy at utility scale (Clark, Richards, and Anchondo 2021). The American Petroleum Institute criticised the plan to eliminate subsidies.

Regarding the role of climate impacts, the framing of climate change has changed as climate change is now dealt with as a threat to national security. Moreover, 2020 was recorded as the second-hottest year in the hottest decade and record-breaking wildfires swept across California (Brown 2021). Extreme weather events, such as the California wildfires in 2018 and 2020, were not crucial for the development of GHG targets, but do tend to push policy and messaging in a more ambitious direction (interviewee #9). Climate change is no longer framed as a purely technological issue, but rather a crisis already underway as evidenced by extreme weather events (Aton 2021a, Song 2021). This might reflect the increasing costs of such events, as 2021 was the seventh consecutive year with 10 or more “billion-dollar disaster events” and both 2020 and 2021 setting new records (Hsiang et al. 2017).

6 Discussion and conclusions

This paper responds to the need to analyse the drivers and barriers of NDC enhancement under the ratcheting mechanism of the Paris Agreement. The role of political, economic and structural factors was proposed and empirically tested based on quantitative and qualitative methods.

We measured NDC enhancement as the enhancement of the 2030 GHG emission target, whether the updated NDC pledged lower total GHG emissions for 2030 than the initial NDC. This indicator is dichotomous and, compared to measures of static climate action, it accounts for change in ambition. We also argue that this measure is more generalisable and a stricter interpretation of NDC enhancement than many other indicators, such as the inclusion of a new non-GHG target, or the addition of new policies and measures, which are relatively undemanding decisions for governments to make. The 2030 emissions target is reasonably rigorous, since it accounts for total emissions reduced by 2030, rather than from a baseline that can be altered in subsequent NDCs. Hence, it is less affected by subtle alterations in baseline scenarios. Finally, the indicator allows for comparisons across all countries in our dataset.

We employed logistic regression in the quantitative part of the study to regress the enhancement of 2030 GHG emission targets on eight explanatory factors. We analysed each potential driver and barrier individually (Figure 1) and as part of a larger model (Table 3). We find that electoral democracy and economic growth are robust predictors of the enhancement of 2030 emission targets. Hence, more democratic countries are more likely to enhance their 2030 GHG emission targets in their NDCs, while rapidly growing countries were less likely to improve on their initial emission targets. Tables 1 and 2 present their estimates with GDP per capita (log) and NDC update year controls. The findings are consistent with results from previous studies that point to the positive role of democratic institutions in general (Bättig and Bernauer 2009), and the participation of a free civil society (Tosun, Béland, and Papadopoulos 2022), elections and civil liberties (Stein 2022) in particular, on the enhancement of climate policy.

The qualitative part of the study extends on this logic with additional analysis on the development process of the updated NDC. Somewhat paradoxically, even though our research process itself shows that it can be challenging to uncover precisely how NDCs were developed, we find that democratic practices, such as transparency, openness part of stakeholder consultations hold the key to understanding why some governments were more likely to enhance their NDC targets. Our sample of case studies had varied NDC development processes. While both South Africa and the US (more limited) held stakeholder consultations, the Brazilian government closed off the development process for its updated NDC. This also led to results expected by the current literature and the quantitative part of the study. Both South Africa and the US enhanced their GHG emission targets for 2030, while Brazil did not improve on its pre-existing NDC pledge. Saudi Arabia, as an authoritarian country, is an outlier that followed a hard-to-access development process that to our knowledge did not involve stakeholder consultations with civil society, but managed to improve its weak initial NDC commitment for the target year of 2030. Nevertheless, KSA's commitments have been only a slight improvement as they do not involve a baseline scenario, and make no definite promises about a shift away from the export of hydrocarbons.

Electoral politics does not show up in the quantitative analysis, but rather emerges as a key issue in the case studies of the US and Brazil (less so in South Africa), where partisanship explains at least the baseline level of climate ambition. It is less clear if it matters for the enhancement of climate targets in a comparative sense, since variation among parties in government is high on the international level. Nevertheless, on the more global level, we do not find that left-wing governments are more likely to

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enhance their NDCs than conservative or nationalist governments. This is broadly in line with Fankhauser et al. (2014), who do not find that government partisanship matters for the passage of climate legislation.

Both the quantitative methods and the qualitative case studies draw out concerns about the future of the economy as a significant barrier of NDC enhancement. The role of economic growth is paradoxical as fast-growing economies were more wary of enhanced commitments and tended to keep their pledges the same or even reduced ambition. Governments with poorly performing economies in the midst of economic recessions were more likely to submit an enhanced 2030 target. In countries with stakeholder consultations (South Africa and the US; Brazil for the first NDC) both business groups and labour organisations showed signs of being alarmed about economic development and the risk of future job losses, which has major repercussions for a just transition away from fossil fuels. Moreover, our expert interviews pointed out that the economic uncertainty of jobs in high-emitting industry and future growth were issues shared by actors in government, labour and business organisations. The quantitative study points towards this as well, as we find that rapidly growing economies are less likely to enhance their GHG emission targets. This finding is also likely due to the worries of governmental and private sector actors about energy needs and the capacity of renewables to generate a sufficient supply of energy for a fast-growing economy (Zhang 2011). Previous literature supports this result by showing that governments tend to face stiff opposition from anxious business groups and labour organisations about potential impacts on economic growth and loss of jobs (Harrison and Sundstrom 2007; Mildemberger 2020). Nevertheless, in all the country cases, the literature and interviewed experts find that business and industry actors are finding the economic arguments of a green transition to renewable energy more persuasive. This is in line with Böhmelt (2013), who shows that show that business organisations influence on climate cooperation is more complex and not always obstructive.

Interestingly, we also find in the quantitative analysis that NDC updates that were submitted during later years were more likely to be enhanced. We surmise that this is due to improved knowledge of advanced emission inventories and scenarios, but it may also be the result of heightened awareness of climate science in general. Furthermore, this result lends credence to the efficacy of the Paris Agreement's "ratchet mechanism", which expects governments to persistently improve on their prior pledges over time. This result may indicate successful policy diffusion as governments learn from previously enhanced NDC submissions (Kammerer and Namhata 2018).

There are at least two policy implications flowing from the present study. First, the ratcheting up of climate commitments is supported by sturdy democratic institutions. This does not mean that we suggest countries simply need to become more democratic to tackle climate change, but rather that the strengthening of open, transparent and meaningful stakeholder engagement can lead to improved climate pledges. This finding is supported by prior policy analyses, which emphasise the need for multi-stakeholder engagement, such as in the case of the Dominican Republic, where the Presidential Council for Climate Change brought working groups across ministries, representatives of subnational jurisdictions, civil society, academia, marginalised and vulnerable groups (Calnek-Sugin 2019; NDC Partnership 2021). Successful stakeholder consultations, however, require necessary resources, expertise, training and planning (BUND 2019). Moreover, institutionalised stakeholder consultation processes with high-level buy-in tend to be more successful at enhancing policy (Fransen et al. 2019). The establishment of the South African Presidential Climate Commission and the Brazilian Forum on Climate Change are a few examples of already existing institutionalised engagement. Second, both the quantitative analysis and case studies demonstrate that the enhancement of climate commitments is highly dependent on alleviating barriers, such as stakeholders' economic worries about future economic growth and jobs.

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Interviewees in the Brazilian and South African cases, specifically, noted that increased ambition was conditional on the ability of climate action proponents to take into account and make a strong economic case for green jobs and a just transition. We find that strategic interventions, which include investments into a just energy transition, have the potential to ameliorate stakeholders' economic worries about enhanced climate targets. By engaging with the concerns of key stakeholders in an open and transparent manner, policymakers can create an added impetus for more ambitious NDC updates. Furthermore, the inclusive development of NDCs may also lead to more effective implementation (Fransen et al. 2019).

This study concentrated on the drivers of and barriers to the development of successive national climate pledges. We analysed domestic factors since the Paris Agreement leaves countries more freedom to decide on their own commitments. Future studies could first of all shed more light on international factors, such as the role of international pressure (e.g., diplomatic pressure) on countries to adopt more ambitious NDCs, the role of major emitters (e.g., does the ambition of other countries depend on what targets are put forward by countries such as China and the United States?), and the role of international institutions such as the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund. Our analysis was also limited to the first round of NDC updates. Further research should continue to shed light on the drivers and barriers over time as countries are submitting next iterations of their NDCs. This will be particularly important to do with all the parts of the Paris Agreement's ratcheting mechanism becoming operational. The first global stocktake of the Paris Agreement has recently started (and is set to conclude at the end of 2023), and Parties' first biennial transparency reports are due to be submitted in 2023/2024. Although we account for the year that the updated or revised NDC was submitted and find that later submissions were more likely to improve on the initial NDC, we cannot control for countries that did not submit updates at all, which we treat as missing data, which future studies with several rounds of NDC updates may want to investigate. Furthermore, the paper did not analyse the extent that the updated NDCs will be implemented. It can be expected that successful implementation (and potential overachievement) of previous NDCs might help raising ambition but that cannot be tested because implementation has just started. Höhne et al. (2017) note that for some countries meeting the NDCs would result in even higher emissions than current trends. Future studies should therefore investigate the implementation of NDCs and the variation between commitments and policy outcomes.

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Appendix A

Figure 2. Correlation Matrix of Drivers and Barriers in the Models

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Appendix B

Table 4. All Variables in a Single Model

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>								
	2030 Emission Target Enhancement								
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Polyarchy	1.939** (0.813)	1.932** (0.834)	1.719* (0.880)	1.269 (0.916)	1.255 (0.926)	1.255 (0.926)	0.976 (1.005)	1.065 (1.013)	1.264 (1.037)
Lef-wing Gov- ernment		-0.371 (0.701)	-0.372 (0.699)	0.026 (0.751)	0.030 (0.752)	0.030 (0.752)	-0.066 (0.764)	-0.106 (0.768)	-0.206 (0.792)
GDP per capita (log)			0.115 (0.151)	0.070 (0.160)	0.080 (0.185)	0.080 (0.185)	0.115 (0.192)	0.123 (0.192)	0.239 (0.210)
GDP growth (NDC2-1)				-0.085** (0.042)	-0.085** (0.042)	-0.085** (0.042)	-0.088** (0.042)	-0.086** (0.042)	-0.035 (0.051)
Avg. Climate Fi- nance (NDC1<t)					29.873 (297.538)	29.873 (297.538)	25.115 (298.263)	26.626 (298.785)	-10.632 (301.108)
Oil+Coal+Gas Rents (NDC1<t<NDC2)							-0.032 (0.045)	-0.029 (0.045)	-0.033 (0.046)
Nr of Affected (NDC1<t<ndc2)								6.627 (9.205)	10.522 (11.209)
NDC update submission year									1.051 (0.643)
Constant	-0.812* (0.436)	-0.692 (0.481)	-1.541 (1.217)	-1.129 (1.263)	-1.219 (1.547)	-1.219 (1.547)	-1.291 (1.556)	-1.451 (1.571)	-2,125.526 (1,299.535)
Observations	111	109	109	105	105	105	105	105	105
Akaike Inf. Crit.	151.448	150.041	151.455	144.937	146.927	146.927	148.408	149.822	149.019

Note: * p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

The dependent variable is the enhancement of the 2030 GHG emission target in the updated NDC (dichotomous). Fossil fuel rents (oil+coal+gas), receipt of climate finance, and the number of people affected by climate hazards are taken as an average during the period between the submission of the initial and updated NDCs. Economic

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growth is lagged by one year from the updated NDC (NDC2). All other variables are measured based on the year of the submission of the updated NDC (NDC2).

Appendix C

Figure 3. Alternative hypotheses: Is quality of government a better predictor of NDC enhancement?

The dependent variable is the enhancement of the 2030 GHG emission target in the updated NDC (dichotomous). Fossil fuel rents (oil+coal+gas), receipt of climate finance, and the number of people affected by climate hazards are taken as an average between the submission of the NDCs. Economic growth is lagged by one year from the updated NDC (NDC2). All other variables are measured from the year of the submission of the updated NDC (NDC2). Point estimates are coefficients from bivariate logistic regression models. Horizontal lines are uncorrected 95% confidence intervals.

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Appendix D

Table 5. NDC country dataset

Country name	Year of initial NDC	Year of updated/revised NDC	Were 2030 emission targets enhanced?
ALBANIA	2016	2021	YES
ANDORRA	2017	2020	NO
ANGOLA	2020	2021	YES
ANTIGUA AND BARBUDA	2016	2021	NO
ARGENTINA	2016	2021	YES
ARMENIA	2017	2021	YES
AUSTRALIA	2016	2021	NO
BAHRAIN	2016	2021	NO
BANGLADESH	2016	2021	YES
BARBADOS	2016	2021	YES
BELARUS	2016	2021	YES
BELIZE	2016	2021	NO
BENIN	2017	2021	NO
BHUTAN	2017	2021	NO
BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA	2017	2021	YES
BRAZIL	2016	2020	NO
BURKINA FASO	2016	2021	YES
BURUNDI	2018	2021	YES
CABO VERDE	2017	2021	NO
CAMBODIA	2017	2020	NO
CAMEROON	2016	2021	YES
CANADA	2016	2021	YES
CHAD	2017	2021	NO
CHILE	2017	2020	YES
CHINA	2016	2021	YES

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COLOMBIA	2018	2020	YES
COMOROS	2016	2021	YES
CONGO	2017	2021	YES
COSTA RICA	2016	2020	YES
CUBA	2016	2020	NO
DEMOCRATIC PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF KOREA	2016	2019	NO
DOMINICAN REPUBLIC	2017	2020	NO
ESWATINI	2016	2021	NO
ETHIOPIA	2017	2021	YES
EU	2016	2020	YES
FIJI	2016	2020	YES
GAMBIA	2016	2021	NO
GEORGIA	2017	2021	YES
GHANA	2016	2021	NO
GRENADA	2016	2020	YES
GUINEA	2016	2021	YES
GUINEA-BISSAU	2018	2021	NO
HONDURAS	2016	2021	YES
ICELAND	2016	2021	YES
INDONESIA	2016	2021	NO
ISRAEL	2016	2021	YES
JAMAICA	2017	2020	YES
JAPAN	2016	2021	YES
JORDAN	2016	2021	YES
KENYA	2016	2020	YES
KUWAIT	2018	2021	NO
KYRGYZSTAN	2020	2021	YES
LAO PEOPLE'S DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC	2016	2021	NO
LEBANON	2020	2021	YES
LIBERIA	2018	2021	NO

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MALAWI	2017	2021	NO
MALAYSIA	2016	2021	YES
MALDIVES	2016	2020	NO
MALI	2016	2021	YES
MARSHALL ISLANDS	2016	2020	NO
MAURITANIA	2017	2021	YES
MAURITIUS	2016	2021	YES
MEXICO	2016	2020	NO
MOLDOVA (THE REPUBLIC OF)	2017	2020	NO
MONACO	2016	2020	YES
MONGOLIA	2016	2020	NO
MONTENEGRO	2017	2021	YES
MOROCCO	2016	2021	YES
MOZAMBIQUE	2018	2021	NO
MYANMAR	2017	2021	NO
NAMIBIA	2016	2021	NO
NAURU	2016	2021	NO
NEPAL	2016	2020	NO
NEW ZEALAND	2016	2021	YES
NICARAGUA	2018	2020	NO
NIGER	2016	2021	NO
NIGERIA	2017	2021	YES
NORTH MACEDONIA	2018	2021	YES
NORWAY	2016	2020	YES
OMAN	2019	2021	NO
PAKISTAN	2016	2021	YES
PALESTINE, STATE OF	2017	2021	NO
PANAMA	2016	2020	NO
PAPUA NEW GUINEA	2016	2020	NO
PARAGUAY	2016	2021	YES

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PERU	2016	2020	YES
QATAR	2017	2021	NO
RWANDA	2016	2020	NO
SAINT KITTS AND NEVIS	2016	2021	YES
SAINT LUCIA	2016	2021	YES
SAMOA	2016	2021	NO
SAO TOME AND PRINCIPE	2016	2021	NO
SAUDI ARABIA	2016	2021	YES
SEYCHELLES	2016	2021	NO
SIERRA LEONE	2016	2021	NO
SINGAPORE	2016	2020	NO
SOLOMON ISLANDS	2016	2021	YES
SOMALIA	2016	2021	NO
SOUTH AFRICA	2016	2021	YES
SOUTH KOREA	2016	2021	YES
SOUTH SUDAN	2021	2021	NO
SRI LANKA	2016	2021	YES
SUDAN	2017	2021	NO
SURINAME	2019	2019	NO
SWITZERLAND	2017	2021	NO
ZAMBIA	2016	2021	NO
ZIMBABWE	2017	2021	YES
TAJKISTAN	2017	2021	NO
TANZANIA, THE UNITED REPUBLIC OF	2018	2021	NO
THAILAND	2016	2020	NO
THE GAMBIA	2016	2021	NO
TOGO	2017	2021	YES
TONGA	2016	2020	NO
TUNISIA	2017	2021	YES
UAE	2016	2020	NO

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UGANDA	2016	2021	NO
UKRAINE	2016	2021	YES
UNITED KINGDOM	2016	2020	YES
USA	2016	2021	YES
UZBEKISTAN	2018	2021	YES
VANUATU	2016	2021	YES
VENEZUELA (BOLIVARIAN REPUBLIC OF)	2018	2021	NO
VIET NAM	2016	2020	YES

Appendix E

Table 6. Semi-structured interviews

Interviewee #	Description
1	Scientific expert involved in Brazilian NDC development
2	Scientific expert involved in Brazilian NDC development
3	Scientific expert involved in KSA NDC development
4	Scientific expert involved in KSA NDC development
5	Climate negotiator and scientific expert involved in the development of the South African NDCs
6	Scientific expert involved in South African NDC development
7	Representative of South African businesses involved in NDC consultations
8	Scientific expert involved in Brazilian NDC development
9	Scientific expert/NGO member involved in the US NDC development
10	NGO representative in the development of the US NDCs
11	Brazilian government executive involved in the development of the first Brazilian NDC
12	Civil society representative involved in South African NDC development
13	Government representative involved in Brazilian NDC development
14	Government representative involved in Brazilian NDC development

PARTICIPANTS

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